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MEDICAL AND HEALTH COOPERATION BETWEEN CHINA AND UZBEKISTAN IN THE CONTEXT OF THE COVID-19

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ABSTRACT

A turning moment for global health collaboration came with the epidemic that swept the globe in 2020. In order to develop adequate sanitary protection of their borders, governments are now making up for lost time by executing multilateral programmes. However, it is crucial to note that Tashkent and Beijing's cooperation in this field started long before the coronavirus became widespread. In this article, there is information about medical and health cooperation between China and Uzbekistan in the context of the COVID-19.

Keywords: medical cooperation, health cooperation, pandemic, COVID-19, global health collaboration.

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МЕДИКО-МЕДИЦИНСКОЕ СОТРУДНИЧЕСТВО КИТАЯ И УЗБЕКИСТАНА В КОНТЕКСТЕ COVID-19

АННОТАЦИЯ

Поворотным моментом для глобального сотрудничества в области здравоохранения стала эпидемия, охватившая весь мир в 2020 году. Чтобы обеспечить адекватную санитарную защиту своих границ, правительства сейчас наверстывают упущенное, выполняя многосторонние программы. Однако важно отметить, что сотрудничество Ташкента и Пекина в этой сфере началось задолго до распространения коронавируса. В этой статье есть информация о медицинском сотрудничестве между Китаем и Узбекистаном в контексте COVID-19.

Ключевые слова: медицинское сотрудничество, сотрудничество в области здравоохранения, пандемия, COVID-19, глобальное сотрудничество в области здравоохранения.

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COVID-19 DAVRIDA XITOIY VA O'ZBEKISTON O'RTASIDAGI TIBBIYOT VA SALOMATLIK BO'YICHA HAMKORLIK

ANNOTATSIYA

2020-yilda butun dunyoni qamrab olgan epidemiya bilan global sog'liqni saqlash sohasidagi hamkorlik uchun burilish vaqti keldi. O'z chegaralarini tegishli sanitariya muhofazasini rivojlantirish maqsadida hukumatlar yo'qotilgan vaqtni ko'p tomonlama dasturlarni amalga oshirish orqali qoplashmoqda. Ammo shuni ta'kidlash kerakki, Toshkent va Pekinning bu boradagi hamkorligi koronavirus tarqalishidan ancha oldin boshlangan. Ushbu maqolada COVID-19 kontekstida Xitoy va O'zbekiston o'rtasidagi tibbiyot va sog'liqni saqlash sohasidagi hamkorlik haqida ma'lumot berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: tibbiy hamkorlik, sog'liqni saqlash sohasidagi hamkorlik, pandemiya, COVID-19, global sog'liqni saqlash sohasidagi hamkorlik.

Introduction

The pandemic that took over the world in 2020 was a turning point for international cooperation in the field of health. Before the coronavirus, this area was far from being the main one, remaining the lot of specialists. Now countries are making up for lost time by implementing multilateral projects to establish effective sanitary protection of their borders. At the same time, it is important that for Tashkent and Beijing, cooperation in this area began long before the spread of the coronavirus, and these close contacts that made it possible to quickly implement a number of joint initiatives and counter the spread of COVID.

In the early 90s of the last century, when Uzbekistan became independent, the situation in health care was quite difficult. On the one hand, the country got a well-functioning primary healthcare system built in the Soviet years, as well as a serious scientific base represented by several specialized institutes. On the other hand, there was almost no production of medicines and other medical supplies in the republic; there was literally not enough of everything from bandages and syringes, not to mention some expensive medicines.

Uzbekistan faced a serious problem of the lack of its own pharmaceutical industry, therefore, in 1993, the state concern Uzpharmprom was urgently created in the country, which included the Uzkhimfarm plant and the Vaccine Research and Production Association.

In the first years of independence, China acted as one of the most important partners of Uzbekistan. The Celestial Empire began not only to provide our country with preferential loans for the purchase of medicines and the necessary equipment for their production, but also invested in the creation of joint ventures. As a result, if in 1994 there were only two pharmaceutical enterprises in the country, then in 2002 there were already 68, in 2012 - 130, and in 2020 - over 190. And all this time, Chinese partners were among the main suppliers of raw materials for medicines, as well as the necessary equipment.

We should not forget about the close contacts established by specialized structures in healthcare. The first meetings of Uzbek and Chinese doctors took place in the early 90s of the last century, and since then hundreds of different events have been held to share experiences.

One of the most important Chinese healthcare projects in Uzbekistan in pre-pandemic times was the Bright Path initiative. Within its framework, in two stages, Chinese ophthalmologists operated on about one thousand Uzbek citizens for free. At the same time, the Chinese side chose

Uzbekistan as the first country to hold this action, because our republic has actively supported the efforts of the Celestial Empire to promote cooperation in the field of medicine in recent years.

Another important step in this work was the signing in November 2019 of a special memorandum between the Ministry of Health, the Women's Committee of Uzbekistan on the one hand and the Ministry of Health of the PRC on the other, which was aimed at implementing a number of humanitarian actions, as well as joint training of qualified specialists in the field of medicine.

Literature review.

One of the most interesting areas of bilateral partnership in the health sector, which has been actively developed in recent years, is alternative medicine. Recall that in Uzbekistan in 2018, the process of classification and certification of the activities of representatives of traditional medicine was launched. As a result, the healers have a real opportunity to establish an exchange of experience with their Chinese colleagues.

According to a presidential decree, in October 2018, traditional medicine was recognized as an additional method of providing medical care. Now it is officially studied in medical universities. Attention is also focused on strengthening the cooperation of educational institutions with leading organizations in this area, including those from China. Such dialogues have already become regular, a number of leading Chinese traditional medicine specialists visited Uzbekistan from 2015 to 2020, they held master classes and trainings for Uzbek colleagues.

Negotiations are currently underway to supply our country with the most advanced digital diagnostic equipment from the Middle Kingdom, and it is planned to implement a number of projects with Chinese investors to produce medicines from medicinal herbs, for which our land is very rich.

For example, Bei Jing Hong Tian Li Pharmaceutical announced plans to invest about \$100 million in the creation of a full-fledged medical cluster, which will have its own hospital, spa and health center and the production of medicines. In addition, in September 2020, the Ministry of Health and the Chinese pharmaceutical company Beizhong Yilin Pharm Tech signed an agreement on the development of traditional medicine and joint research in this area.

Analysis and discussion.

The most important stage of this work was the opening in mid-2020 in Tashkent of the Uzbek-Chinese Center of Traditional Medicine, which is designed to become a center for the preservation and promotion of people's health and a bridge for the development of mutually beneficial cooperation between Uzbek and Chinese traditional healers. It diagnoses diseases and treats patients based on unique Chinese methods using acupuncture, various types of massage, herbal and other environmentally friendly medicines.

The pandemic that swept the world in 2020 has become a key factor in the development of cooperation in healthcare between the two countries. Uzbekistan was one of the first to respond to the outbreak in China and urgently delivered two consignments of medical supplies there.

In addition to efforts at the government level, the Uzbek people have also taken active steps to help China contain the epidemic. For example, Murojon Kenzheboev, a student of the International University of Foreign Languages in Guangdong Province, a native of the Uzbek city of Gulistan, purchased at his own expense more than 20,000 medical masks, which he handed over to teachers and students of his native university.

When the first case of COVID-19 infection was detected in Uzbekistan on March 15, the Chinese government quickly decided to provide humanitarian assistance. The first batch was handed over to the Uzbek side on March 30, including medical devices for testing and personal medical protection kits. On April 28, the second batch of humanitarian aid arrived in Uzbekistan. Then organizations such as the Chinese Academy of Sciences, the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Affairs, and many others extended a helping hand to Uzbekistan. During the most difficult period of the spread of infection in our country, they provided the most necessary medical products, medicines and personal protective equipment.

At the invitation of the Uzbek government, on April 17, a joint medical working group sent by the Chinese government arrived in Uzbekistan. She visited more than 30 medical institutions in seven cities, held lectures and consultations, sharing her experience with Uzbek colleagues.

The head of the joint Chinese medical working group, Luo Lisheng, said that the doctors not only fought the disease shoulder to shoulder with their Uzbek counterparts, but also reached an agreement to further strengthen exchanges and cooperation in the field of healthcare. “In the future, China will continue to share anti-epidemic experience with Uzbekistan through the remote medical systems of the two countries,” the Chinese specialist said at the time.

One of the largest joint projects during the pandemic was the launch of the production of the Uzbek-Chinese vaccine against coronavirus ZF-UZ-VAC2001 in Almalyk. An agreement on the production of the drug was signed in August 2021 between the Chinese biopharmaceutical company Anhui Zhifei Longcom Biopharmaceutical Co. Ltd and the Uzbek enterprise Jurabek Laboratories. According to the agreements, 10 million doses of the drug per month are initially bottled at facilities in our country. In the future, the volumes will be increased to 200 million doses per year. The parties also reached an agreement on the transfer of Chinese vaccine production technology and advanced training of Uzbek scientists and specialists in China.

Conclusion.

According to Kristina Dzhurakulova, a leading researcher at the International Institute of Central Asia, from the very beginning of the pandemic, the countries of Central Asia and China have shown themselves to be truly strategic partners.

“China is one of the most promising partners in the healthcare sector. A clear confirmation of this is how effectively the country managed to resist the pandemic. In the shortest possible time, the spread of the coronavirus was brought under control.

In the new realities, interaction in the area of public health and ensuring sanitary and epidemiological safety is becoming an important area of international cooperation. The development of this area lays the foundation for long-term sustainable development,” she said.

In this context, the proposal of the President of Uzbekistan to increase cooperation with China in pharmaceuticals, traditional medicine, as well as to improve the qualifications of doctors and establish partnerships between specialized hospitals meets the long-term interests of all parties. This will allow us not only to cope with the current pandemic, but also to prepare for possible future threats.

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